

Practical Guidelines for Volunteer Activities

SocialErasmus+: supporting the organisation of volunteer activities and community engagement during international student mobility

*"How to set up a volunteer initiative
from A to Z"*

*"A learning-centred approach to
volunteering"*

 SocialErasmus+

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About the project

The **SocialErasmus** programme incorporates all volunteer activities where international students engage with locals to contribute to their local host society. The **SocialErasmus+ project** is an Erasmus+ KA3 Forward-Looking Cooperation grant project to support the development and professionalisation of the SocialErasmus initiative across Europe.

The main aims of the project are:

- Better integrate the international exchange student in the local society by organising volunteer opportunities to ensure an exchange of values takes place between the International students and the local community
- Developing and professionalise the implementation process of the activities by involving more stakeholders such as Higher Education Institutions and local schools in the process.
- Increasing the learning experience of students by engaging with Higher Education Institutions and Non-Formal Education experts to build in elements of Community Service Learning in the curricula and increase the recognition students receive for their volunteering activity.

The SocialErasmus+ project has a focus on **Erasmus in Schools activities**, to ensure also local youth experience internationalisation and intercultural communication in classrooms from a younger age.

The implementation of the SocialErasmus+ project is coordinated by ESN and implemented with the support of the European University Foundation, Youth for Exchange and Understanding, Erasmus Student Network Besancon, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, University of Vienna and the University of Vigo.

Erasmus in Schools

Erasmus in Schools is a project coordinated by the Erasmus Student Network where local ESN associations organise visits to schools so that our exchange students can do a wide range of activities that include country and culture presentations or workshops, language sessions and activities promoting mobility.

Learning from Experiences

Students have a different learning experience, interacting directly with international students, putting theory into practice in an international and intercultural setting, allowing for non-formal education methods to be included in Education with a focus on the development of competences.

Integration through social engagement

By encouraging international students to volunteer in social activities in their host community, the students will be able to interact with locals, experiencing local traditions and better understand the local context. Allowing internationals to contribute to the local community, will increase their connection with their host community.

Internationalisation and Global Citizenship

Erasmus in Schools fosters a positive attitude towards multicultural societies and opens up the students' mind to the international and interconnected global society which we currently live in, introducing the world of international student mobility to the students.

Intercultural Awareness

Building intercultural awareness to increase understanding of different cultures is important for both the Erasmus student and the local school students to overcome prejudice and ensure acceptance of intercultural diversity

Practical Guidelines

This practical guide will help local coordinators who want to implement Erasmus in Schools activities by
Glossary: In order to ensure that all

- ESNER / ESN coordinator: the coordinator of the activity from the local ESN Section is referred to as the ESN coordinator or the ESNER.
- Erasmus/International students: either of the two can be used: “Erasmus students” or “International students” will refer to the international students registered as a member of your ESN section that will visit the school with you and facilitate the activity.
- School pupils: the word pupils is used to define the minors registered in the local primary and high schools to clearly distinguish between them and the international students.

Within your ESN Section

It is important to approach the idea of implementing an Erasmus in Schools activity during one of your team meetings in your section. The activities need people to coordinate the activities, and if you are the Erasmus in Schools coordinator you will take the lead, but it might be the case that you need support from your team members to successfully implement the activity. Things that need to be discussed the moment you want to launch Erasmus in Schools activities within your section that needs other people in your section be involved:

Coordination: Who will take part in the coordination of the activity? Try to set up a small core team that will do the activity.

Discuss how to find schools: does the section have contacts to local primary or high schools?

Social Impact: present the activity and its potential impact to the University. Showcase the types of activities that can be executed by the students and the topics that can be covered. Once the activities take place, it is also a good idea to show.

Volunteering on the Day: Anyone can be a volunteer during an Erasmus in Schools activity and support the implementation. All you need is motivation and knowledge on how to work with a team. The ESNers accompanying the student on the day will facilitate the activity and help the international students in case of difficulties, to animate or re-launch the debate, support the division in the room etc.

How to partner up

In order to implement the project with maximum impact, it is important to put the learning experience of the students central in the implementation. To ensure the learning experience of the student is maximized, it is important to engage multiple stakeholders in order to establish long lasting cooperation.

Lasting cooperation will allow for the setup of an activity framework where the activities are carefully planned, executed and evaluated in order to improve future activities.

It is important that clear agreements are made on who takes care of which steps in the process and who coordinates which aspect. This will be further addressed in the next chapter.

The three key players that can help ensure a successful implementation of Erasmus in Schools' project is the **local ESN organisation**, the **Higher Education Institution** and the local primary and secondary **schools**.

Finding schools

Finding a school that has time to welcome you for an Erasmus in Schools activity, can sometimes be a challenge.

ESNers: Volunteers are current university students and were once high school pupils. They might still be able to get in touch with some of their previous teachers. You can ask some of your volunteers to see if they still have contacts in the area.

Cultural Events: During local cultural events, do not hesitate to go and talk with teachers that may be present.

Partner Organisations: Look for partners that organise similar activities in schools: for example, the Young European Federalists and Europe Houses intervene in schools to promote European citizenship.

University Contacts: Introduce the activity to your contacts at your university, chances are they have contacts with schools in the area. If the university supports the project - they can help you get in touch with the schools.

City youth council or local/regional education department: You can approach your local youth council and the education department to introduce the project and ask them to spread your call.

School Groups or Teacher Organisations: The national board can contact school groups or teacher Organisations that could be interested in the topics brought forward in Erasmus in Schools type of activities.

National student organisations: Contact the National student council for high school students to introduce the students to the International student councils.

National Agency: The National Agency working on Erasmus+ also has a responsible person working with schools. They have contacts in schools that are interested in internationalisation and thus might be interested.

During Open Days or student forums: During these events, you can meet teachers or school representants with whom you can talk about Erasmus in Schools activities.

Contacting a distant school: Through them, the access will most likely be easier as they have fewer opportunities to talk about mobility.

In the toolbox you will find a flyer that explains Erasmus in Schools and the benefits of an Erasmus in Schools activity.

Involving the teacher

Once a teacher has agreed to organise an activity in their class, It is important you clearly explain the goals of Erasmus in Schools and specifically the sessions you plan to do. Share the Activity Outline with the teachers to share the content and methods you plan to use in their classroom. Ask for their feedback in order to engage the teachers.

It would be advised to have a pre-meeting (physical or virtual) with the teacher to discuss the activity. It will allow you to check out the school and it's environment and engage the process of creating the activity. If the international student who will attend the activity is already selected, you can implicate him in the process as well so that both parties are aware of what is expected during the activity

Important information for ESN to address to the teacher:

Flexibility: Tell them you will do your best to find students, but communicate your limitations clearly; do not make promises you might not be able to keep with regards to frequency of your visits, amount of students or a certain student profile the school is looking for.

Responsibility: As an ESN coordinator your main responsibility is the well-being of the Erasmus student and offering interested Erasmus students the opportunity to take part in a school visit.

Presence: you should expect the school teacher to stay present during the session. They do not need to intervene, but as the students are minors, it is better to not be left alone.

Debrief: The students will have a short debriefing about the activity during the session, if the teacher wants to talk about what the students have learned about the visit of the international students themselves, you can invite them to do this separately.

Language barriers

To avoid language barriers it is important that a local ESN volunteer is present that can take a coordinating role to communicate with the Erasmus students, school, teachers and pupils.

It would be best to have a teacher who knows a minimum of English in order to facilitate communication between all people involved. In case the school would not be able to host English speakers - which can always happen in for example primary schools - search for students that know the local language or try to create an activity that requires less language and focuses on activities and games.

Universities

Although smaller scale Erasmus in Schools projects can be implemented without the involvement of Higher Education Institutions, their support can be valuable to support the recognition of the volunteering experiences of the student. This certainly becomes important if the implementation is set up as a series of activities.

One of ESN's long term goals is to get more recognition for the volunteering activities that our students take part in. Ideally, we want to embed volunteering initiatives in the Curriculum, allowing for the recognition of the competences students gained by volunteering during their mobility.

In order to ensure there is proper evaluation and validation of the gained skills, we propose to embed it in the curriculum under the concept of Service-Learning. The Erasmus programme of the European Union allows for a perfect opportunity to give meaningful opportunities for exchange students to take part in International Service-Learning.

Without the support of the Higher Education Institution, it will not be possible to embed SocialErasmus+ activities in the curriculum and provide a framework of community service learning to improve the learning experience of the Exchange students.

Service-Learning (sometimes referred to as community based or community engaged learning) is an innovative pedagogical approach that integrates meaningful community engagement into the curriculum and offers students academic credit for the learning that derives from volunteer engagement within community to apply their gained knowledge in practice by working on a real-world problem (Aramburuzabala P., McIlrath L., et al., 2016).

Find out more about the role of the University in the Educational Framework. You can share this document with your University or Student representatives working on the educational reviews of your institution. Be aware that Institutional change takes a long time.

Involve the Universities

Having the support of your university's International Relations Office may help with consolidating the project to the schools. There are many ways you can collaborate with your University on the development of Erasmus in Schools and other SocialErasmus activities:

A lower level of involvement:

Start involving your University slowly, these are things you could ask of them if your relationship is still fresh:

- **Letter of Support:** an official support letter can convince Schools in the vicinity of the University that the project is serious
- **Signing of Certificates:** You could ask the University to (co)-sign the certificates for the volunteers, increasing the recognition given to the document
- **Insurance coverage:** You can check if the insurance policy of the university covers students when they are out on a volunteering activity

Higher Level of Involvement:

If you have a long-standing relationship with your University, and you believe your goals are aligned, these are things you could work on together:

- **Reimbursement of Expenses:** if the actions align with the intentions of the University, it might be possible for the University to reimburse the expenses for the travel/material

The involvement of the University can start off small. You can reach out to your International Relations Office explaining the project you are implementing and asking them for support.

- **Content support:** If you want to work out a specific activity with a specific learning objective that you wish to address even more in the future, it would be possible to collaborate with some of the faculty staff in the University working on the topics. For example, you can involve the Department of Political science if you wish to create a session on the European Political system
- **School Network of the University:** Universities often have good connections with schools in the area. If the University is involved in your local community, they might already have interesting contacts.

Make tandems with local organizations/ local students. In every city, there are associations involving different publics that are already going to schools to promote European citizenship, international mobility and cultural diversity. You can contact them and offer to organise common activities and meetings. Very often other organisations have educational material that can contribute to bringing you new ideas or new sessions to implement in your activities.

Define Activity Setup

It is important to clearly define the activity framework and ensure that all stakeholders involved are aware of this. Do not underestimate the amount of time it can take to come up with a common framework. It is, however, an important step that needs to happen before you can start.

With this, we mean that you have to coordinate with the stakeholders involved, agree on the timeline to be followed before the activity and define who will have what responsibility.

Asking these questions up front is the best way to make sure that you are on the same wavelength. It will help you with the actual preparation phase and prevent you from having to go back to the school with additional questions.

Practical and Logistical

It is important to discuss all the practical and logistical questions there might be before entering the school. Asking these questions at the beginning will help you understand what is possible during your activity and will prevent you from having to look.

The Erasmus in Schools platform and the Activity Outline will help you go through the majority of these questions in order to know the practical setting for the session. Questions:

- **Dates:** Which are the possible dates the event should take place. Is it feasible for all parties on these dates? Make sure this does not conflict with
- **Location:** Where will the activity take place? How easy is it to reach the location with the Erasmus students.
- **Room:** It is important to know what the room will look like in order to prepare for the activity? What type of tables/chairs are there? Can the tables and chairs be moved? What type of facilities are there; is there a beamer or whiteboard that can be used during the session? Is there a space you can
- **Age of the Pupils:** In order to adjust the content of the session to the target audience
- **Duration:** How long can the activity be? Will the session be cut if the time is too short?
- **Regulations:** Are there specific rules to follow in the school?
- **Classroom dynamics:** How is the atmosphere in the class, are there specific points of attention?

Topic Selection

It is important to define the topic you would like to address with the teacher and the school. It is best to adjust your proposal based on the course you will be visiting, align with the learning objectives of the course.

Learning objectives that define an expected goal of a curriculum, course, lesson or activity in terms of demonstrable skills or knowledge that will be acquired by a student. These learning objectives are usually set for each course by the ministries of education and/or educational authorities.

In order to convince the teachers of the sessions you will present, it is important to keep this in mind. It is also important to see what the role and added value of bringing an international student to the session.

Example:

Bringing a Spanish student to a Spanish language course or a history lesson about Latin America, might be more interesting than bringing the same student to a geography class.

Questions:

- Topic: Is there a specific topic the school would like to address?

Legal aspects

In certain countries, there might be some legal aspects you should follow up on. Discuss with the school what

It is important to define the topic you would like to address with the teacher and the school. It is best to adjust your proposal based on the course you will be visiting, align with the learning objectives of the course.

would be needed for international students to enter the school's territory and the classrooms to work with children. In certain education systems, it might be needed that the student proves not to have a criminal record.

Questions:

- **Legal documents:** Does the school require any type of legal document in order for the student to enter the school territory.
- **Pictures:** Is it possible to take pictures during the activity?

We usually agree with the school that only one person from the ESN section will be taking pictures and the school will be shown the picture selection before the pictures will go live. You can offer to make the pupils of the schools unrecognisable by taking pictures from the back, focusing the pictures on the international students.

Role definitions

Make sure that the tasks are well defined and each person is aware of what is expected of everyone. Discuss with the school how involved they wish to be in the development of the activity.

ESN Coordinator's role:

The ESN Coordinator takes an active role as the facilitator of the session, depending on the experience the international student has on facilitation experiences themselves. If they feel confident enough, they could do parts of this.

Teacher's role:

It is the best that the teacher takes a more passive role in the activity. The strength of an Erasmus in Schools activity is that students are able to talk peer-to-peer and discuss topics in an interactive way. Some small support in the facilitation can be asked of the teacher.

Things to keep in mind the facilitator should do:

- Introduce the visitors and the aim of the session
- Be a go-between between the school pupils and the international students.
- Integrate the pupils into the activity, induces them to ask questions, overcome their shyness
- Rephrases questions to students to make concepts clearer
- Helps in case of difficulties (understanding, discussions)

Agree upon the role of the ESN Coordinator, International student, and school teacher before, during and after the activity.

Questions:

- Involvement of the teacher: Is the teacher going to take part in the activity or are they going to be spectators?
- Activity Outline: Would they like to give feedback on the outline of the session?
- Introduction: Ask if it is Ok for the ESN Coordinator to introduce the visitors to the class and the aim of the session.

Ask the teacher **to stay present** in the room during the session. It is better not to be alone with minors, and the ultimate responsibility for their care stays with the schools

Evaluation

It is important to determine how you plan to evaluate the activity. Discuss with the school what is the role of the participant and the role of the teacher in the debriefing process of the activity.

The participant will include a short debriefing activity to wrap up the activity in itself. We would, however, advise that the teacher takes a bit of time to discuss what the pupils learned from the discussion with the international students. The final responsibility of the learning of the students lays with the school and the teacher - we would advise that the teacher takes a bit of time at the end of the class or the beginning of the next class to discuss with the students what they learned from the discussion with the International student(s).

This can happen at the end of the class and involve the International students, or take place in the next class with the students alone. The ESN coordinator can host a short debriefing to wrap up and evaluate the activity. Tips on how this can be done will be included in chapter 6.

Start small

It is important not to overwhelm the school with a huge project proposal. Start small with one or two visits, after which you can evaluate and upscale your activity. Do not make promises you might be able to keep.

#Erasmus Upgrade
MANIFESTO
vision to the future of Erasmus+
outcomes of consultation & exchange
13 points, 5 chapters
- 27.04 - release
- press conference, release & stream
- multi-channel release
- 26-weeks campaign to follow
CORIMA

Promote the activity towards the International students

Every International student can be involved in an Erasmus in Schools activity.

Bring it to the attention of the students that you will be hosting Erasmus in Schools activities. Do you plan to host Erasmus in Schools activities during the semester? Present the concept during your introduction session during the Welcome Days of your university.

Take a look at the campaign that has been made to promote taking an active role in society during their Erasmus by volunteering on exchange. The material is made available online in the toolkit. Use the videos that have been made to introduce the activities.

Engage International students

When students sign up as members of ESN and get their ESNcard, you can record if they are interested in taking part in Erasmus in Schools / Social Inclusion activities in order to be aware of who wants to take part in this type of activities.

Once you have the concrete information of the activity, you can use the Erasmus in Schools platform to spread the actual activity through the emails from the registration at the start of the semester as well as your social media accounts to promote the activity.

The Erasmus in Schools platform will allow you to create an activity outline that can be spread among your students and allows the students to sign up for the activity so you can see who is interested.

Important to give the student the confidence to take part:

- **Be inclusive:** any international student can participate regardless of their nationality and mobility type.
- **Number:** very often international students feel more confident when they know they do not need to do this alone. They can develop an activity with one of their international classmates.
- **Coordination:** As ESNer you will be involved in their activity and support them with the practical implementation of the activity. Make sure they know you will offer them support and they are not on their own in this activity.

Prepare for the Activity

Involvement of the student

It is important to involve the students in the preparation of the activity. It would be best to have a preparation meeting with the students in order to prepare the activity together. In this preparation meeting, you can clarify what the activity will actually look like and ensure that the student feels confident in the preparation of their part in the session - whether this is a powerpoint, poster or anything else.

Ask the teacher **to stay present** in the room during the session. It is better not to be alone with minors, and the ultimate responsibility for their care stays with the schools

Briefing session

As mentioned in the introduction, it is important to involve the student before the activity. These are the topics you should address during your Take-In session to properly brief the students.

Agenda for Briefing session:

1. Explain the goal of Erasmus in Schools and why it is important to take part in these type of activities. See the SocialErasmus Charter and the Erasmus in Schools flyer.
2. Explain the Institutional education structure of the country/region briefly so the international student understands the education system.
3. Inform the students about the context that was discussed with the school in Chapter 3: Define Activity Framework to give all the information to the students, they should have as much information as the ESNers on the practical arrangements for the visit. You can even invite the teacher for this briefing meeting if he/she would be available.
4. Share what you expect from the International students, make sure they understand their responsibilities and what they can expect from you.
5. Define Topic and Method: Discuss the topic you wish to address during the activity and discuss with the participants what they would like to do. You can show them the Activity Outlines and some of the models so you can come to one new idea.
6. Next Steps: Agree on the next steps together with the students: what is the timeline for them to complete the activity outline and the materials to prepare for the activity? Will you have another meeting to finalise the activity and do a test run?
7. Logistics: Where will the activity take place, how will you go there? Try to make sure you have enough time to go through the activity.
8. Task division: Who will be responsible for what by when?
9. Questions: make sure there is enough time for debriefing and discussion at the end of the event.

How to create the activity is addressed specifically in the Activity Development Guideline that can be shared with the student.

Do not hesitate to rehearse the session to make the students feel more confident about their activity. When doing a read through of the activity, it will be easier to divide who will be speaking at which point.

SocialErasmus+ Results

Throughout the large scale implementation period from September 2018 until June 2019, more than 1.292 SocialErasmus activities took place across Europe where international students volunteered in their local communities, among which 262 visits to local schools.

271 Cities in Europe

31 Countries

1.292

SocialErasmus activities

86.034

People involved

2.526

ESN volunteers

18.574

International students

Volunteering on Exchange

262

Erasmus in Schools visits

10.442

Local school students

438

ESN volunteers

1.324

International students

1 ESN volunteer

coordinates activities,
8 international students volunteer
and engage with 25 locals.

Intercultural understanding
& Transcultural Competence

87%

Intercultural
Communication Skills

Active citizenship
& Social Responsibility

90%

Project & Activity
Management

82%

Erasmus Spirit &
European Citizenship

81%

SocialErasmus Competence Framework

students were asked which competences they felt they gained by joining community engaged activities.

Inspiration for events

During an Erasmus in Schools you can discuss a large range of subjects and subjects with the students that can be adapted to the needs of the class. Important is that you adapt your activity according to the pupils' age and language skills.

Think out of the box, it is possible to focus on gastronomy, cultural traditions such as traditional feasts such as the Chinese New Year, Venetian Carnival or Japanese tea.

Take a look at the different models presented below to inspire yourself, or take a look at the Activity Outlines prepared by ESN Coordinators across Europe.

I'm a migrant, so what?!

Time allocation:
90 min

Age of participants:
15 - 19 years old

Size of the group:
25

Aim

- Present migration as a natural process happening since the beginning of time
- explore the values & challenges brought by migration
- Encourage acceptance and understanding toward topic of migrations

Activity

This activity starts by introducing a mindmap with post-its around the topic of Migration, Immigration and Emigration. A simulation game is implemented to showcase the challenges newcomers can experience in society. the international student shares the their personal story and the classroom discusses how inclusive their society is to newcomers.

What do you know about me?

Time allocation:
90 min

Age of participants:
15 - 19 years old

Size of the group:
25

Aim

- Raising awareness about stereotypes and their impact on our society
- Raising awareness of stereotypes of their own country
- Breaking down stereotypes

Activity

This activity explores the concept of stereotypes the class has about their own country as well as the country of the Erasmus student. The class will discuss if these stereotypes are correct for themselves and the international student and reflects on the effect stereotypes can have on people and group dynamics.

Country Quartet

Time allocation
60 min

Age of participants
10 - 12 years old

Size of the group
25

Aim

- Teach children more about the local culture of different countries.
- Have the children interact with students from different countries.
- Break through some of the stereotypes that the children might have about certain countries.

Activity

This activity targeted at younger children focuses on a country quarter. The pupils receive a poster that they are supposed to fill with pictures of traditional cultural elements of the international students; from the capital, to the colour of the flag, to pictures of an important statue and traditional food, in order to challenge them to learn more about the different countries.

Implementation

If everything in the preparation phase goes well and all steps were followed, the activity will run smoothly. There are a few things you can keep in mind to ensure you support the international students during the activity. The coordination of the activity by an ESNer is core if you wish the event to be successful but during the event, the ESN coordinator should take a step back and give the spotlight to the international student.

Supporting the student

Communication:

- Introduce the Erasmus in Schools Activity to the classroom and introduce the International students to the class.
- Ask the pupils in the class to also briefly introduce their names, this makes the activity more personal.
- Be in touch with the teacher during the activity to see how they are experiencing the session.

Linguistic:

- Try to do the entire activity in English if this was planned with the teacher. If any of the instructions need to be translated to facilitate the implementation of the event, do this by summarising the instructions very briefly in the local language.
- Helping to communicate with the pupils in case there are linguistic or cultural barriers. Explain to

students that experiencing these barriers is also an important lesson.

- Helping with translation and interpretation if technical things are not understood by the students.

Technical:

- Be mindful of the time, keep a clear overview of the activity but try to be flexible based on the input from the students.
- Help with technical support;
- Circle the room to make sure that the pupils are mindful of the International students trying to facilitate the session.

Emotional:

- Give space and trust to the international students to deliver the workshop it is important that they feel empowered to do the activities.
- Actively support them during the activity with encouraging gestures, give positive signs that the workshop is going well and encourage participants to be active.

Emergency (stepping in):

- If the pupils are not interested and/or the student is lost you can potentially step in to change the format/method.
- Helping to lead the discussion if it's not going well by redirecting the audience to stay on topic.
- Dealing with the troubling audience if the student is not able to involve them/correct them.

Communication about the activity

Try to have an ESN volunteer present who can take pictures and takes care of the communication of the event. Focus on the interpersonal aspect in the pictures, highlighting the international students working together with the children and make sure the activity is brought well. Images showing what happens during the activity says more than a standard group picture.

NOTE: Agree with the school what you can do with the pictures you take during the activity. Involve the school by asking them for permission to publish pictures live and engage the school on social media and/or link to their website. If necessary, offer to make the pupils of the schools unrecognisable by taking pictures from the back, focusing the pictures on the international students.

Evaluation

Debriefing

In order to link back to the Experiential Learning theory of Kolb, it is important to organise a reflection session with the participants. In order to make sure that the participants have learned from the activity it is important to have a debriefing. You can follow the debriefing cycle introduced by Roger Greenaway in the Active Reviewing Cycle (Greenaway, 1993). You should aim to have a short debriefing with each of the groups that are involved, however, the purpose of the debriefing is, of course, different in each of the debriefing.

Stage	Goal	Questions to ask
Facts	Get all of the information out in the open	- What happened? What did you see? hear? think?
Feelings	When emotion is present, make sure they practice expressing it in a productive way.	- How did you feel about it? Is this a good or a bad thing?
Findings	Make every experience an opportunity to learn.	- What can we learn from this experience? What can we gain from this?
Future	Take what has been learned and turn it into more productive behaviours and smarter choices.	- How can we use/apply what we have learned? What is going to be different the next time?

With pupils

It is always nice to end the activity by debriefing very briefly with the students. Take the final ten minutes of the activity to discuss what they experienced and how they feel about it. What is their point of view on discussing this with someone coming from a different country? Do they feel it impacted their willingness to experience student mobility themselves?

Purpose of the debriefing:

1. Learning objectives: Do the pupils feel they know more about the topic the students brought to the class to discuss with them?
2. Intercultural Learning: Did the pupils learn something about the importance of intercultural dialogue? How do they feel about going on mobility themselves?

Tip: Use the debriefing questions mentioned above to discuss how the students experienced the activity.

With International students

Purpose of the debriefing:

1. Facilitation Skills: How did the international students feel after facilitating the activity in the classroom?
2. Intercultural Learning: what did the international student learn about other cultures through this activity?

Important: disseminate the SocialErasmus student survey to the international students in order for us to better understand the learning undergone by international students during volunteering activities while they are on exchange.

With teacher

Ask the teacher if you can stay a bit longer after the activity to exchange impressions and get feedback from him/her. If not possible, see if you can meet with the teacher during the break or ask the teacher to send an email later on.

Debriefing with the teacher is a good way to show them that you are concerned about their satisfaction. It will help you improve the Erasmus in Schools activity and might help you plan for the next visit to the school.

Purpose of the debriefing:

1. Learning objectives: were the learning objectives that were discussed up front met?
2. Logistics: How did the logistical preparation go?
3. Future: Would the school be interested in repeating an activity? What would they change in this case?

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*We do not need
magic to transform
our world. We
carry all of the
power we need
inside ourselves
already.”*

– J.K. Rowling

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